

SOP 12s SsoFast Probe realtime PCR for the detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* eggs

For DNA extraction from the faeces please refer to SOPs for the magnetic capture of *Echinococcus multilocularis* eggs from red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) faecal samples, before proceeding to the realtime PCR steps.

1. Aim of method

This method describes the molecular identification of *Echinococcus multilocularis* DNA using a realtime PCR method with a 12s target and SsoFast probes. This molecular method follows on from the DNA magnetic capture fishing method described in separate SOPs with either manual or automatic washing protocols.

2. References

- 2.1. Isaksson M, Hagström Å, Armua-Fernandez MT, Wahlström H, Ågren EO, Miller A, Holmberg A, Lukacs M, Casulli A, Deplazes P, Juremalm M. A semi-automated magnetic capture probe based DNA extraction and real-time PCR method applied in the Swedish surveillance of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) faecal samples. Parasit Vectors. 2014 Dec 19;7:583.

<https://parasitesandvectors.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13071-014-0583-6>

3. Method summary

After magnetic capture of EM DNA from red fox faeces a realtime PCR is carried out in duplicate with an extraction blank control as well as positive and negative wells controls on each plate. A positive sample is indicated by a valid amplification curve, and with a cycle threshold (Ct) below 40.

In regions where EM is not endemic further confirmation of positive findings should be carried out by using either a second realtime PCR method based on different markers for the mtDNA (e.g Øines et al. 2014 - mtCO1 assay) and/or with sequencing using the Cest1 and Cest2 primers (NADH). A parallel sample should also be analysed to confirm the findings of a positive result.

At the start of each analysis period, it is important to verify new batches of reagents and each step of the process using positive control material. This method does not use PEC (positive extraction controls) in each sample given the risk for cross-contamination and challenges with analysing the B-samples for secondary verification.

4. Principles

This method describes a realtime PCR method for detecting EM DNA, after magnetic capture of EM from fox faeces, based upon the amplification and detection of the fluorescence signal once it exceeds the detection threshold level. The realtime PCR uses nucleotide primers to amplify a short region of the *Echinococcus multilocularis* target. A specific nucleotide probe, complimentary to the Em target DNA, is used to increase the specificity of the PCR.

It is important to follow good laboratory practice (GLP) routines for molecular work to avoid contamination, and ensure best possible results. Follow your molecular laboratory's routines for this, or consult resources such as OECD guidelines for quality assurance in molecular genetic testing (<http://www.oecd.org/science/emerging-tech/38839788.pdf>).

5. Warnings/HMS measures

EM is a zoonotic parasite and therefore the laboratory needs to follow their HMS guidelines with regard to limiting exposure to this parasite. Infection occurs via the oral transmission of EM eggs and can result tumour like growths in a number of internal organs, including the liver and brain.

Minimum HMS requirements are that all samples are frozen prior to handling to inactivate any potential oocysts (-80°C at the core of the sample for a minimum of 48 hours) and that gloves are used at all times even after freezing.

6. Chemicals and Reagents

Table 1 List of chemicals and reagents used to carry out the EMrtCO1 realtime PCR method

Description	Contents	Provided by	Article no.	Used at step:
Forward primer	Primer Em12s MGB F [10µM]	Various commercial vendors		9.1 (prep) (9.2.1 probe in master mix)
Reverse primer	Primer Em12s MGB R [10µM]	Various commercial vendors		9.1 (prep) (9.2.1 probe in master mix)
Realtime PCR Probe	EmMGB_P [10µM]	Various commercial vendors		9.1 (prep) (9.2.1 probe in master mix)
In Master mix and as Negative control	Nuclease free water			9.1 (prep) (9.2.1 in master mix) 9.2.2
Positive control	EM DNA from positive material			9.2.2
Realtime PCR mix	SsoFast Mastermix	Bio-Rad, USA		9.1 (prep) (9.2.1 in master mix)

7. Controls

Description	Contents	Provided by	Article no.	Used at step:
DNA negative control	Nuclease free water			9.2.2
EM positive control	DNA extracted from positive EM material	EU NRL for parasites		9.2.2
EBC: Extraction blank control	RNAase/DNAase free water			9.2.2

These controls need to be included in every PCR plate run. The EBC control is placed in its own column on the plate and closed before any of the positive samples are added to the plate. The EBC demonstrates the absence of nucleic acids in the reagents during the entire PCR process.

8. Equipment and instruments

Equipment that is critical for the method is marked with an asterix. Should something other than this equipment be used then the method will require further validation steps at your laboratory to ensure equivalence.

Table 2 List of equipment that is needed to carry out the Echinococcus multilocularis DNA magnetic capture method

Item	Description	Producer	Article number	Used at step ^a :
Vortex	Table top vortexer	Various vendors		9.2.2
Table-top centrifuge				9.2.2
PCR plates with cap-strips	Each plate has 96 wells divided into			9.2.2

Item	Description	Producer	Article number	Used at step ^a :
	12 columns with 8 wells each.			
Realtime PCR machine	Applied Biosystems 7500 Fast instrument	Life Technologies, USA		9.3
Pipettes with filter tips				9.2.1 9.2.2
Computer software for analysing Ct values				9.4

^aUsed at step indicates the step where that equipment is used. For disposable single-use equipment each entry represents each time that equipment type is needed anew.

9. Workflow and full method description

Sample registration and identification carried out per your own laboratory instructions and the work sheet/laboratory records for your laboratory should be used to note additional information about the samples.

Figure 1 *Echinococcus multilocularis* Em12s SsoFast probe realtime PCR workflow

9.1. From Magnetic Capture automatic/manual washing SOP

9.1.1. Defrost sample - the sample can be placed on the workbench to defrost whilst the master mix is prepared and added to the PCR plates. After 10-15 minutes, the sample will be defrosted and ready for use.

9.2. In Pre-PCR facilities/Clean Room - preparation step

9.2.1. Prepare master mix for PCR in the clean room. The table below shows the volume needed per sample analysed. Calculate the total volume needed for the total number of samples to be analysed. You need to bear in mind that each sample should be analysed in duplicate.

Description	Volume per sample (µL)
Primer Em12s F [10µM]	0.6
Primer Em12s R [10µM]	0.6
Em FAM or HEX MGB_P [10µM]	0.2
SsoFast M Mix	7.5
Nuclease free water	4.1

Prepare the mastermix, beforehand, in 1.5mL tubes that can be transferred to the pre-PCR laboratory.

9.2.2. Prepare the PCR plates in the pre-PCR facilities

1. Add 13 μL of the master mix to each well. There are 12 columns per plate with 8 wells in each column.
2. In one column add 2 μL EBC to each well. Close this column before going to the next step (negative control). Close using a cap-strip and NOT FILM.
3. In four wells add 2 μL negative control (dH_2O) to one column. Close before going to the next step (the adding of sample DNA).
4. Vortex the DNA samples and spin down on a table-top centrifuge before adding 2 μL of the DNA template to the well containing the master mix.
5. Seal filled sample wells with a cap strip (again don't use a film).
6. Now add 2 μL positive control to four wells at the end of the plate, isolated in their own row to avoid contaminating the other samples.
7. Transfer the filled PCR plate to the post-PCR facilities to run the realtime.

Each sample has to be analysed in duplicate. Either by using two wells for each sample or alternatively by making a duplicate second plate. The choice will depend on the number of samples being analysed. Each plate can be used to analyse 80 samples with the remaining 16 wells used for controls (EBC: 8 wells; negative control 4 wells; positive control 4 wells).

9.3. In Post-PCR facilities - running the realtime

Place the plate in the realtime machine in fast mode (ramp rate 5°C per second) and program the following settings*:

- 2 minutes at 95°C
- Then 48 cycles of 95°C for 5 seconds and 60°C for 30 seconds.

Data collection is done in the VIC-channel (For HEX coloured probe) For FAM, make sure it collect data using this channel also.

9.4. In Post-PCR facilities - analysing the results*

- 9.4.1. Open the realtime PCR result in software program.
- 9.4.2. Click on 'analyse' button
- 9.4.3. A graphical visualisation of the results will now be produced in a "Results" tab
- 9.4.4. Move Threshold line to linear part of the amplification curve on the positive control (Y axis in log), and above level for noise (often at threshold between 100 and 300). Check negative and EBC controls.
- 9.4.5. Check for presence of characteristic exponential amplification curve shapes from samples.

*(Description based on the analysis using Applied Biosystems 7500 Fast Instrument and relevant software. Other systems may require other procedures.)

10. Interpretation and reporting of the results

- 10.1. In general, a Cq value equal to or less than 40 is considered positive provided one or more of the curves indicate exponential growth and successful amplification of PCR products. However, multiple factors can effect the signal and the results cannot be purely based on the Ct values alone. Therefore, curves with higher values that show exponential growth at later cycles, for example as a result of PCR inhibition in the samples or samples with very low concentration of DNA at the start, might also be positive and should be investigated further. Presence of inhibitors or other substances may interfere with amplification efficacy.

- 10.2. In non-endemic areas further validation is required to confirm positive or suspected positive findings. We suggest to carry out a second realtime PCR using a different mitochondrial target on the A and B samples as well as repeating EMrtCO1 PCR on the B-sample.
- 10.3. The results are reported as EM detected/not detected

11. Storage of the Samples

- 11.1 The remaining sample DNA can be frozen for future analysis.
- 11.2 The PCR plate is carefully discarded as detailed in point 12.2 below.

12. Disposal of waste materials

Follow your laboratory guidelines for the disposal of biohazardous waste.

- 12.1 Gloves and paper waste are autoclaved prior to disposal as normal waste.
- 12.2 The remains of the biological samples and equipment that has been in contact with the biological material is disposed of in a yellow biohazard container, which is sent for incineration once full.